

**UNDERSTANDING LEVEL OF REGULAR TEACHERS'
COMPETENCY IN INCLUSIVE SCHOOL: A STUDY ON PEDAGOGY
COMPETENCY UNDERSTANDING TO CHILDREN WITH
SPECIAL NEEDS IN INCLUSIVE SCHOOL**

Tias Martika¹, Abdul Salim, Munawir Yusuf

Master of Special Education Program, Sebelas Maret University, Indonesia

Abstract:

The aim of this research is generally to determine level of regular teachers' competency in inclusive school in Surakarta city, Sukoharjo regency, and Klaten regency. To be more specific, this research aims to: (1) determine regular teachers' background in inclusive school, (2) have ever been involved in inclusive education training, (3) determine and understanding the level of pedagogy competency of children with special needs in inclusive school. The subjects used in this research are 45 high school regular teachers of inclusive school in three regencies/cities, namely, Surakarta, Sukoharjo, and Klaten. Data is collected through questionnaire, interview, and documentation. The collected data is then analyzed by descriptive statistic. The result of this research shows that education background of high school regular teacher of inclusive school is mostly specific subject teacher. From 45 respondents, only two respondents have been ever involved in inclusive education training. Meanwhile, it is known that the understanding level of pedagogy competency to children with special needs is still low. It can be concluded that low competency of pedagogy to children with special need in inclusive school is caused by regular teachers in inclusive school that mostly have non Special Education background and never participated in inclusive education training.

Keywords: pedagogy competency, regular teachers, inclusive school

¹ Correspondence: email tiasmartika@gmail.com

Introduction

Every child has right to get education. An ideal education is an education without considering gender, race, religion, ethnic group, and culture, even disability of a child. This is in line with international issue in nature of education, Education for All (EFA). In attempt to succeed Education for All (EFA), international world refers to Declaration Human Right 1984 on article 26:

"... (1) everyone has the right to education. Education shall be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Elementary education shall be compulsory. (2) education shall be directed to the full development of the human personality and the strengthening of respect for human right and fundamental freedoms. It shall promote understanding, tolerance and friendship among all nation, racial or religious groups, (3) parents have a prior right to choose the kind of education that shall be given to their children."

Inclusive education is education for all. Implementation of inclusive education is different in each country. Diversity of perception and idealism about inclusive education is the reason of the different implementation. In European country, education for children with special needs is mostly merged with regular students. Farrell (2005) mentions that inclusive school in England, especially in his homeland, use curriculum suitable with children's competency. Beside, educator for Children with Special Education Need (SEN) is required to own QTS (Qualified Teacher Status) certificate in special education.

The implementation of inclusive education in Indonesia is varied caused by different perception and understanding of inclusive. Tarmansyah (2009) in his research about inclusive education in Padang City found that the implementation of inclusive education is still in the form of integrated education. Major obstacle faced is there is no formal reference about implementation of inclusive education yet.

Education in Indonesia starts to switch from segregation to inclusive. Based on PP no. 70 Year 2009 Article 1, inclusive education is an education management system giving chance for all students having disability and special need to attend education in education environment together with normal students.

Data from Direktorat Pembinaan PKLK Dikdas (2013) shows that there are around 925 school (elementary, junior high school, senior high school, and vocational high school) in 2007 and increase in 2013 to 2.100 school. In Surakarta, data of inclusive school is as follow:

Tias Martika , Abdul Salim, Munawir Yusuf –
 UNDERSTANDING LEVEL OF REGULAR TEACHERS' COMPETENCY IN INCLUSIVE SCHOOL:
 A STUDY ON PEDAGOGY COMPETENCY UNDERSTANDING TO CHILDREN WITH
 SPECIAL NEEDS IN INCLUSIVE SCHOOL

Year	School	Students	Teachers' Assistance
2016	16	46	38
2015	15	46	39
2014	15	46	39

Though the number of inclusive school increases every year, the implementation of inclusive school does not correspond yet with inclusive school target.

One of the most important aspects in inclusive education is teacher, who has direct contact with students with special needs. Teacher is a human component in teaching and learning process, which has role in attempt to build potential human resource. Sardiman (2001: 1) argues that in practice of inclusive education in regular school, education for students with special need is given to teachers' assistance. Direktorat Jenderal Mandikdasmen (2010) elaborates teachers' assistance task: (1) arranging assessment instrument together with class teacher and subject teacher, (2) building coordination system among teacher, school administration, and students' parents, (3) accompanying handicapped students in learning together with class teacher/ subject teacher, (4) giving special help for special students who face difficulty to learn in regular class, in the form of remedial or enrichment, (5) giving continue guidance and making notes for handicapped students during learning activity, and it should be understandable for new teacher, and (6) giving help (sharing) to class teacher and/or subject teacher so they can give education service for special children.

Regular teacher in inclusive school should possess special competency in giving education service for students with special needs. According to Mulyasa (2004: 37-38) competency is assimilation among knowledge, skill, value, and behavior reflected in thinking and act habit. One competency that regular teachers in inclusive school should have in giving education service to students with special needs is pedagogy competency.

Suryanto and Jihad (2013: 43) explains that pedagogy competency is teachers' competency for children, education designing and implementing, study result evaluating, and students' development to actualize their potential. Pedagogy competency in term of special education is a way of how teacher can give service by understanding students' flaws and also maximizing competency of student with special needs.

In giving educational service for students with special needs, pedagogy competency can be considered as important point. By possessing pedagogy competency, in this case is special education pedagogy, a teacher can give education service appropriate with the ability and need of students with special needs.

Fact in field shows that not every school has teachers' assistance. In Surakarta itself, there are 4 schools having no teachers' assistance from all 16 inclusive schools. It makes

students with special needs do not get appropriate service. The students with special needs in inclusive school that do not get teachers' assistance will be handled by regular teacher or their class teacher.

This research is generally aims to explore level of regular teachers' competency in inclusive school in Surakarta city, Sukoharjo regency, and Klaten regency. To be more specific, this research aims to (1) determine regular teachers' background in inclusive school, (2) have ever been involved in inclusive education training, and (3) determine, the understanding level of pedagogy competency of children with special needs in inclusive school.

Method

This research is a kind of case study research. This research used high school regular teachers' of inclusive school in Surakarta city, Sukoharjo regency, and Klaten regency as subject. Instrument to collect data is questionnaire. The questionnaire used is modified questionnaire from Gunarhadi, dkk (2015) with Cronbach Alpha reliability measurement with 0.91 reliability. Collected data is analyzed by using descriptive qualitative.

Result and Discussion

Result

The data shows that regular teachers in inclusive school have education background which is not suitable yet for inclusive education service. Beside, intensity of joining training about inclusive is still low. It shows that regular teachers' competency pedagogy of special education in inclusive school is still low. To be more specific, it can be elaborated as follows:

A. Regular teachers' education background in inclusive school

From answered questionnaire about regular teachers' education background in inclusive school, it can be known that 0% from special education, 7% from counseling, 89% is subject teacher, and 4% from psychology.

The data can be shown in the form of diagram below:

Figure 1: Regular teachers' education background in inclusive school

From the result above, it can be known that most regular teacher in inclusive school have inappropriate education background in handling children with special needs.

B. Regular teachers' participation in joining inclusive training

There are only two respondents, or it can be said as 4%, have ever participated in inclusive training once. Meanwhile 96% respondents never participate in inclusive training yet. The data can be shown in the form of diagram below.

Figure 2: Regular teachers' participation in joining inclusive training

C. Pedagogy competency of special education

The result of measuring regular teachers' pedagogy competency of special education in inclusive school is shown in table below.

Tias Martika , Abdul Salim, Munawir Yusuf –
 UNDERSTANDING LEVEL OF REGULAR TEACHERS' COMPETENCY IN INCLUSIVE SCHOOL:
 A STUDY ON PEDAGOGY COMPETENCY UNDERSTANDING TO CHILDREN WITH
 SPECIAL NEEDS IN INCLUSIVE SCHOOL

Respondent	Score	Criteria	Respondent	Score	Criteria
1	44	Low	24	48	Low
2	50	Low	25	73	Good
3	59	Enough	26	71	Good
4	63	Enough	27	59	Enough
5	51	Low	28	49	Low
6	46	Low	29	32	Very low
7	61	Enough	30	53	Low
8	32	Very Low	31	45	Low
9	54	Low	32	44	Low
10	54	Low	33	57	Enough
11	38	Very low	34	33	Very Low
12	59	Enough	35	29	Very Low
13	29	Very low	36	33	Very Low
14	54	Low	37	42	Low
15	67	Enough	38	66	Enough
16	39	Very Low	39	73	Good
17	63	Enough	40	35	Very Low
18	47	Low	41	44	Low
19	31	Very Low	42	46	Low
20	42	Low	43	49	Low
21	30	Very Low	44	37	Very Low
22	45	Low	45	68	Enough
23	51	Low			

Table 1: Regular Teacher's Pedagogy Competency Score of Special Education in Inclusive School

The data can also be presented in the form of graphic below:

Figure 3: Regular Teacher's Pedagogy Competency Score of Special Education in Inclusive School

From the result of regular teacher's pedagogy competency score of special education in inclusive school, it shows that regular teachers' pedagogy competence of special

education, 27% is very low, 44% low, 22% enough, 7% good, and 0% very good. This percentage can be presented into pie diagram below.

Discussion

The result of regular teachers' pedagogy competency of special education shows that most regular teachers in inclusive school have low pedagogy competency of special education. This result is in line with research from Bukvic, Z. (2014) observing teachers' competency in inclusive school showing that from 70% teachers have low knowledge about teaching students with special needs, and their attitude is mostly negative. In the other hand, young teachers have high competency. Some teachers that have positive attitude of inclusive education prefer not to teach student with special need.

Other research is done by Gunarhadi, dkk (2016) with title *Pedagogic mapping of teacher competence in inclusive schools*. The research shows that most teachers in inclusive school have limited knowledge and skill. Teachers have not only lack of experience in teaching students with special needs, but also lack of education in terms of quality.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on result and discussion above, it can be concluded that understanding level of regular teachers' pedagogy competency is still low. It is mainly caused by teachers that have non-special-education background and lack of joining training about inclusive.

Recommendations

1. Making a peer teaching to share information about knowledge and handling of children with special needs in inclusive school.

2. Holding periodic meeting about inclusive training program.
3. Providing guide book for teacher to develop regular teachers' pedagogy competency of special education in inclusive school.

References

1. Bukvic, Z. (2014). Teachers competency for inclusive education. The European Journal of Social and Behavioral Sciences (EJSBS), 1586-1590. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15405/ejsbs.141>
2. Direktorat Jenderal Mandikdasmen. 2010. Permendiknas Tentang Pendidikan Inklusif Bagi Peserta Didik yang Memiliki Kelinandan Memiliki Potensi Kecerdasandan / atau Bakat Istimewa. Kementerian Pendidikan Nasional
3. Farrell, Michael. (2005). Key Issues in Special Education. London : Routledge
4. Gunarhadi, Sunardi, Andayani, T.R., & Anwar, M. (2016). Pedagogic mapping of teacher competence in inclusive schools. Prosiding ICTTE, 1 (1), 389-394
5. PP No. 70 Tahun 2009.
6. Tanpa Nama. 2013. Pedoman Penyelenggaraan Pendidikan Inklusif. Jakarta: Direktorat PKLK Dikdas
7. Tarmansyah. 2009. Pelaksanaan Pendidikan Inklusif di SD Negeri 03 Alai Padang Utara Kota Padang. Pedagogi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Pendidikan. Vol IX No 1 Hal 1-16

Tias Martika , Abdul Salim, Munawir Yusuf –
UNDERSTANDING LEVEL OF REGULAR TEACHERS' COMPETENCY IN INCLUSIVE SCHOOL:
A STUDY ON PEDAGOGY COMPETENCY UNDERSTANDING TO CHILDREN WITH
SPECIAL NEEDS IN INCLUSIVE SCHOOL

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Special Education Research shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).